

Chromium and dolomite removal from rotary filter cake in chrome chemical industries

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Production of chromium compounds from chrome ores is considered as major inorganic chemical products. The production line utilizes chromium ores, dolomites and soda ash. As a result of 200 kg products per ton of raw material, 702 kg sludge is generated by vacuum rotary drum filters. Based on waste minimization, recycling and recovery of raw material from the sludge have been conducted. The filter cake contains 12% chromium and 74% dolomite. Various proportions of dried cake are recycled, maximum recycle proportion being 25% without any changes in the final product. Material balance is conducted with and without recycle for justified product. The partial recycling the dried solid waste saves raw material and reduces partial transportation costs.

Chromium is extracted from its ore by alkaline or acidic dissolution. The finely grounded chrome ore is roasted with sodium carbonate under oxidizing condition at 1100°. Sodium chromate is leached out from the calcinated gangue as most of the gangue is insoluble. The solution contains hexavalent chromium which is reduced with sulfur dioxide and converted to a useful product in crystallized form as sodium dichromate. The dichromate is converted to chrome oxides such as CrO₃ and Cr₂O₃, which are used in electrolysis and metal coating applications¹.

Among the exporting chromium ore countries, Iran contribute less than 1% of world chrome ores with only 2 million tons reserved mines, compared to main chrome ore reservoir in South Africa with 828 million tons². Besides South Africa, the main exporting countries for chrome ore are Russia, Philippines and Turkey. The industrialized countries such as Japan, USA, Germany and France are the major countries importing chrome ores for metallurgical and chemical purposes³. In 1993, the production of chrome chemicals in Iran was reported to be about 103803 tons. About 6% of chrome ore was used for internal use, and the rest used for exports. The rate of production of chrome ore was increased to 355000 tons in 1994⁴. A 3.5-fold increase in production of chrome ore was achieved.

The chrome chemical plant is located in the north of Iran. In the process of production of chrome chemicals from chrome ore, lime is added prior to roasting followed by leaching in hot water. At this stage, the insoluble solids are

retained by filtration process. A series of rotary filters for recovery of dissolved chrome from the insoluble solid sludge are used. The sludge is generated through separation of extracted solution from insoluble inorganic matter by the rotary drum filters. The daily production rate of sludge is 23 tons, stored at the plant site for maximum dewatering. The partially dehydrated sludge is transported and land-filled.

The purpose of the present work was to minimize waste, make use of the filter cake for chrome recovery, improve overall plant efficiency without any changes of product quality and reduce transportation costs.

Results and Discussion

The process of roasting took place at high temperature using kiln for oxidation. Since aluminium oxide and silica are present in the ore along with sodium chromate, sodium aluminates are formed. Leaching the chemical from the roasted material by dissolving in hot water was the next stage. The required amount of lime based on stoichiometric ratio may prevent dissolving of sodium aluminate. Since roasting was accomplished at high temperature, therefore it is possible that part of solid materials to be dissolved in the liquid solution and solid-liquid phase reach an equilibrium point. Addition of dolomite may shift the melting point, as diluting material for roasting was required. Usage of dried recycle filter cake enriched with 8–10% chrome with make up sodium carbonate was required to meet the correct stoichiometric ratio. Complete recycle of solid waste may

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cause additional impurities in the final product, therefore, usage of defined proportion of recycle ratio was based on stabilization of fixed chemical composition of final product.

Suspension of solid in the leaching tank after sufficient residence time for dissolving solid and mixing the slurry was autoclaved with steam, then the heat-treated solid-liquid mixture was filtered using a series of rotary drum filters. The filtered solution was clear enriched with sodium chromate, then sulfuric acid solution was added to form sodium sulfate, which was recovered through centrifuge. Application of sulfur dioxide gas in presence of sodium hydroxide caused the dichromate to be converted to chromium hydroxide and sodium sulfate, which was recovered as byproduct from the process. The mixed solid-liquid solution was filtered for separation of insoluble solid. The clear solution was concentrated and the product was extracted from the solution in a crystallization process. Sodium sulfate and sodium dichromate are used in various industries.

Chromium compounds were extracted from chromite ore in roasting (oxidation) process followed by leaching with an alkali or acid. The fine powdered ore was roasted in presence of sodium carbonate under oxidizing conditions at 1100^o. The sodium chromate was leached out from the calcinated gangue, as most of the gangue contained insoluble minerals, ash from ore. The soluble part was filtered and the insoluble mud was retained by rotary drum filter. The solution containing hexavalent Cr was reduced to sodium dichromate using sulfur dioxide as reducing agent. The crystallized dichromate was converted to chromium oxides (Cr₂O₃ and CrO₃). In the process of extraction of chromium compounds from chrome ore, the filter cake was analyzed for chrome recovery. The dried recycle filter cake for various proportions were considered. The process was affected by oven temperature and the drying time. The maximum rate of recycling was determined without any significant changes of chemical composition of the final product. The drying processes for filter cake were carried out at 100, 120 and 150^o for one hour.

Fig. 1 shows that more than 86% of the moisture was removed within one hour of drying at 150^o. The problem associated with the filter cake was its stickiness and highly corrosive nature to metals. Special screw type dryer was required to be designed for this process. The drying time was increased to 2 h when the oven temperature dropped to 120^o. The remaining moisture was less than 8%. The experimental results indicate that the dried filter cake with moisture content of more than 10% fed to the system created thermal problem in the roasting zones. The thermal shock may cause changes on chemical composition of the final product.

Fig. 1. Percentage of moisture reduction of filter cake with respect to drying time at various oven temperatures

Analyses of filter cake and final product were conducted to monitor the material balance. The analysis of each stream was based on weight of feed and product. The results are shown in Table 1. The material balance based on input and output analysis shows that limited recycle ratio can be used, which has no significant effect on the composition of the final product.

Table 1 Material balance for production of chrome chemicals without recycling the filter cake

Material	Stream no			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Chromite ore, kg	320	-	-	-
Dolomite, kg	466	-	-	-
Sodium carbonate, kg	214	-	-	-
Sodium bichromate, kg	-	200	-	-
Carbon dioxide	-	-	98	-
Chromium oxide Cr ₂ O ₃ , kg	-	-	-	42.4
Chromium oxide CrO ₃ , kg	-	-	-	22.6
Ash, sludge from ores, kg	-	-	-	637
Total, kg	1000	200	98	702

The analysis of dried filter cake was carried out in several experimental runs. Table 2 shows the feed composition with 14–30% of filter cake recycled, and the maximum allowable ratio was 25% with the same final product. The analysis of the final product obtained is shown in Table 3.

The results show that maximum recycle rate of 30% maintained the required product composition.

Table 2. Material balance for production of chrome chemicals with recycling the filter cake

Material	Stream no.						
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
Chromite ore, kg	290	290	-	-	-	-	-
Dolomite, kg	282	282	-	-	-	-	-
Sodium carbonate, kg	214	214	-	-	-	-	-
Sodium dichromate, kg	-	-	200	-	-	-	-
Carbon dioxide, kg	-	-	-	98	-	-	-
Filter cake, kg	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Chromium oxide Cr ₂ O ₃ , kg	15.1	-	-	44.6	29.5	15.1	-
Chromium oxide CrO ₃ , kg	8.05	-	-	23.8	15.75	8.05	-
CaO, kg	56.25	-	-	166.05	109.8	56.25	-
MgO, kg	63.2	-	-	186.5	123.3	63.2	-
Ash, sludge from ores, kg	107.4	-	-	317.05	209.65	107.4	-
Total, kg	786	1036	200	98	738	488	250

The daily transportation rate of sludge generated by rotary drum as filter cake from chrome chemical industry was calculated to be 23 tons.

Table 3. Effect of recycle filter cake on final product

Recycled filter cake, %	Chromite ore %	Dolomite %	Solubility in water, %	Ratio of solubility
0	32	46.6	25.52	89.5
14	30.32	36.24	25.5	89.4
15	30.2	35.5	25.5	89.3
20	29.6	31.8	25.45	89
22	29.36	30.32	25.41	89
25	29	28.1	25.32	88.9
30	28.4	24.4	24.3	85.2

Fig. 2 shows the annual rate of sludge produced from filter cake for duration of 4 years (1993–1996). When the production rate was increased the sludge generated was also increased. The major expense involved, is the transportation of sludge to the landfill site for proper disposal. The transportation costs increased by 34% during 1993–1994 as the production rate was increased by 23%, then the transportation costs were drastically increased by 103% as the production rate was increased only by 10% during the

Fig. 1. Annual rate of filter cake, sludge generated and transportation expenses.

period of 1994–1995. The transportation expenses were annually increased due to fuel price rise. During 1995–1996, the production rate was fixed and the transportation expenses increased by 67%. During 1997–2000, the transportation expenses increased more than 70% as the fuel price increased by 50%.

Conclusion : Recycling the residues from filter cake based on experimental results would reduce at least 30% of transportation expenses. In addition, about 10% saving on chromium ore and 40% on dolomite may show a great saving on raw materials and transportation costs. In order to achieve this goal a suitable dryer must be designed for handling the filter cake with moisture content of about 50%.

Experimental

The raw materials available for production of chrome were chromate ores. Sodium chromate and dichromate were produced by roasting chromium ore in presence of lime or dolomite (MgCO₃ and CaCO₃) in a kiln. Dolomite consisted of 29–35% CaO, 16–21% MgO and 42–46% CO₂. The chrome ore was grinded as fine powder (200 mesh), mixed with appropriate proportion of lime and sodium carbonate prior to roasting.

In the process of chrome recovery through filtration of insoluble solid from leaching tank using rotary filter, the filter cake was dissolved in hot water tank for several times then continued for recovering more chrome in a sequential series of filtration process as recommended. The retained filter cake was very sticky with high moisture content and also very corrosive. The solid waste required to be stored in the plant site for a day for dewatering prior to any transportation. The solid waste contained 8% chrome.

The raw material, chromate ore (FeCr₂O₄) contained other impurities such as Al, Mg, Ca, SiO₂ and V. Chrome

has melting point of about 1900° [2, $1900^{0.2,5}$]. It easily dissolved in the mineral acids. The chrome ore consisted of 48–53% Cr_2O_3 , 10–15% Al_2O_3 , 10–15% Fe_2O_3 , 5% SiO_2 , 8–10% moisture and 7% ash, the rest having a very small amount of other metal oxides such as MgO and FeO . The chromite ore (FeCr_2O_4) for chrome chemical industry, the ratio of $\text{Cr} : \text{Fe}$ in the ore, less than 2 : 1, is more suitable. Chromium was extracted from its ores by dissolving in an alkaline or acidic solution. The fine powdered chrome ore was roasted, followed by the sodium chromate being leached out in a hot solution by a reducing agent such as SO_2 . The concentrated solution was subjected to crystallization and the product $\text{Na}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ was converted to CrO_3 . Analysis of the dried filter cake showed that it consisted of 6% Cr_2O_3 , 3.2% CrO_3 , 22.5% CaO and 25.3% MgO . The filter cake (1 g) was dissolved into a distilled water (50 ml), heated for 5 min after it reached to its dissolving point, then filtered. A 20 ml of filtered solution was treated with 5 ml

of 0.1 *N* ammonium ferrous sulfate solution (More's salt), then titrated with 0.1 *N* of KMnO_4 solution to determine chrome oxide CrO_3 concentration.

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